

Sharifov Akmal Mamadaminovich
Public Safety University of the Republic of Uzbekistan
graduate student
akmalsharifov98@gmail.com

The essence of the food supply system

Abstract: this article describes the concept and structure of the food supply system. Although the concepts of food supply and food security are used in the same sense. From the history of the origin of food supply to the current issues of food supply, it is covered.

Key words: food supply, category, food security, food independence, population food consumption, production, resources.

The transition from the planning and distribution system to the market and the state's management of the economy, the food support of the country's population was provided by market elements and the power of food expansion. The loss of economic security in the total consumption of imported products creates a dependence on the global food market, which increases the instability of the domestic market. A sharp decrease in food imports in August 1998, which creates conditions for political and economic pressure on the country's exporters, is against their national interests. Therefore, there is an urgent need to formulate fundamentally different state policies in the field of food support, the need to justify the target attitude, strategic and tactical directions and tactics.

Quantitative assessment of the level or state of food security of the country can be done using the dynamics of two groups of indicators:

- the level of consumption of basic food products, taking into account their differences in groups of the population with different incomes;
- the degree of self-government of the country with food.

In both groups, real and deficient indicators are distinguished, i.e. Minimum (maximum) allowed. In the first group of indicators, medical standards can be previously used scientifically based social standards. Current and forecast indicators of the financial and economic status of producers, including food imports, are used.

In January 1996, the State Duma of the country adopted a decision "On measures for the food security of the country and the supply of food products to the population." Based on it, the law "On Food Safety of the Country" has not yet been signed by the President of the country and has been reviewed by the State Duma. As part of the system of legislation on national security issues, the law regulates the state policy on the supply of food products to the population, as well as legal relations in the field of production, storage, processing and distribution of products. Protect the company in general and every a citizen separates threats and negative factors from threats and negative factors related to lack of consumption or low-quality food. The main purpose of the law is to guarantee the population's right to full nutrition as one of the conditions for the realization of human rights, for the realization of the rights to life, other non-citizen rights.

Due to the development of the above laws and doctrines on food safety, many researchers reduce the problem of food safety to the problems of food safety, but the food supply system includes a wide range of them.

The security of the food supply system or food safety defines the limiting parameters of the system, the violation of which creates threats to the security of the country. In other words, safety is one of the conditions or one aspect of the food supply system. This is the difference between the concepts of food safety and food security.

As for the term food supply, it has long been widely used in economic literature, but

the food supply system has not been singled out as an independent research topic. As a rule, food problems were taken into account in the context of the general problem of agricultural development or the general problem of organizing the supply of food products to the food market.

Under the conditions of an open economy, the justification of the meaning of the food aspect in the country's economy and the development of the agro-industrial complex should be based on the political, socio-ecological goals of development and the skills of state priorities. The main importance of the state is the goals of the political tone, among which the leading place is occupied by food security, which is the provision of access to food in an unlimited amount of time for the state and society, and sufficient and extraordinary for the healthy and social development of everyone in personal conditions. the minimum necessary to maintain health and working capacity under the circumstances. It follows that in the development of agricultural policy, the state has a sufficient degree of ownership of the power of the population, at least in terms of stopping the population's energy imports. The need to ensure a certain level of production is determined by two main reasons. First, if the level of own production is not enough to electrify the government for the minimum standards, then there are negotiations on large-scale political and economic issues of the state, additional possibilities of pressure have been created in the country. complete suspension of food imports (trade embargo) to temporarily deny humanitarian aid in case of famine and other natural disasters. Secondly, the food market and most of the imports directed to the world market are the stability of the domestic market, therefore the whole economy is more volatile than the world markets in developed countries and there are almost no regulators. The second level is the goals of a socio-ecological character. Agriculture, in addition to production, performs a number of important functions: socio-demographic, cultural, ecological, recreational and spatial-communication. Therefore, when deciding to expand or reduce agrochemical production, it is necessary to take into account the damage caused, especially in the ecological and social spheres. These goals are mostly in nature. In accordance with these target devices, agriculture is based on the environmental technology of the area, its permissible technological loads, soil fertility and the standard of living of the population.

The third-level goal of economic development in the hierarchy of goals (other indicators of economic performance). They play a major role in developing development strategies, political and socio-economic goals in the form of restrictions. Thus, it is necessary to increase the economic efficiency of industries and enterprises in the implementation of restrictions of a political and socio-ecological nature in each place. The first group of goals dominates the federal level, the second is the provincial level, and the third is the level of individual enterprises.

It was considered that the food supply system consists of three subsystems: food consumption and nutrition of the population, actual production of food products, formation and distribution of food resources.

The goals and objectives of the bulk system of consumption of heat, approved by the government of the country in August 1998, can be justified on the basis of the concept of public policy in the healthy nutrition of the population, as approved in August 1998:

- human health is the most important priority of the state;
- food products should not harm human health;
- nutrition should not only meet the physiological needs of a person in food, but also perform preventive and therapeutic tasks;
- reasonable nutrition of children should receive special attention of the state;

- Nutrition should contribute to the protection of the human body from unknown environmental conditions;

- Healthy nutrition requirements are unified for all food products.

The criterion for assessing the nutritional level of the population is the level of meeting structural needs and the energy content of the food diet. The minimum nutritional level of the population in the amount and assortment of food, the minimum acceptable level in terms of the amount of nutrients and energy supply leads to the consumption of the consumer.

The main factors that reflect food safety are the absence of substances harmful to health in food or their concentration should not exceed the recommended level.

The subsystem of food production is mainly agro-industrial production. The level and pace of agro-horizontal production industries, their potential for expansion determine the country's food resources and food security.

The main field of agriculture is agriculture. First, the country's food production capabilities depend on the natural and economic conditions of its activity. A prerequisite for food security is food independence, which includes meeting food needs through local production. The idea is that the growth of the production of local Agro-Sanif Complex stimulates the development of many sectors of the economy.

To increase the interests of increasing the level of food supply for the population and the development of the agrochemical complex, it offers to use the opportunities of the International Labor Department and the world market. Based on the circumstances that alleviate the situation in the import food market, it helps to replace the shortage of local food, improve the range and quality of the population, and also plays a certain positive role in the formation of a competitive environment in the domestic market. However, it is not allowed to subsidize the subsidized goods of the exporters of domestic producers in the domestic market. Based on the interests of ensuring food security, it is necessary to increase the dependence of agriculture, food and processing industry on the import of material and technical resources, as well as agriculture, food and processing industry.

One of the important conditions for the country's food independence is the effective operation of domestic tractors and agricultural machinery, mineral fertilizers, plant protection products, veterinary drugs, and technical means of the processing industry.

However, self-sufficiency for food, calculated as the ratio of domestic production to domestic consumption, does not indicate a country's level of food security and is therefore a generalization indicator. cannot be. It should be noted that in some countries, in some countries, the export of food and agricultural raw materials leads to poverty, and in other countries, on the contrary, in the import of food. contributes. At the same time, both groups are not dependent on food, because in the first case, the basis of food imports, as well as the export of economically highly developed countries, allows to guarantee the payment of food and raw materials necessary for them. necessary for them.

The subsystem of formation and distribution of food resources describes the level of physical and economic supply of food to different categories of the population, the state of the food market, the state of the food market, the size of the state food reserves.

The physical freedom of food means that it is not included in the corresponding payment capacity and is distinguished by its quantity and the population required in the retail network and food markets. As the volume and structure of food supply and the structure of rules adopted for them.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be said that a special problem is the development of food products in the northern regions, the minimal opportunities for the development of agricultural production, limited to dispersion, fishing, fisheries, greenhouse plants and animal husbandry in imported feed. Away from the highly efficient commodity production zones, their food supply (including imports) is increasingly used for food and raw materials production (including imports) and for further development of secondary stocks. In order to develop more. For the northern regions, traditional food sources that supply agricultural products, seeds, fodder, young animals, so used "backyard" agricultural enterprises.

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